

ELECTRICAL PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE AND ITS ROLE IN PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE SYSTEM RELIABILITY IN INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the implementation and effectiveness of Electrical Preventive Maintenance (EPM) programs in industrial facilities using the 5Ms of Management Framework: Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money, to determine challenges, their influence, and their role in achieving sustainable system reliability. Data were gathered from 26 maintenance personnel in a PEZA-accredited industrial park through structured survey questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, supported by qualitative responses and guided by the 5Ms framework. Results revealed that overall, EPM was partially implemented. The Method and Machine dimensions were rated fully implemented, indicating that planning, scheduling, and technical maintenance procedures were generally in place. In contrast, the Man, Material, and Money dimensions were rated partially implemented, reflecting gaps in workforce training and certification, resource availability, and budget allocation for EPM. In the Philippine Economic Zone Authority (PEZA), compliance with EPM is monitored mainly through the Certificate of Electrical Inspection (CEI), which requires submission of electrical test reports and safety certifications in accordance with the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC). However, this compliance does not provide comprehensive guidance for sustained preventive maintenance implementation, highlighting the need for a localized and sustainability-oriented EPM framework. The findings emphasize the importance of structured training programs, standardized documentation systems, proactive resource planning, and dedicated maintenance budgets to strengthen operational reliability and ensure long-term industrial sustainability.

Keywords: *Electrical Preventive Maintenance, System Reliability, Industrial Maintenance, Sustainability, 5Ms of Management, Engineering Management*

INTRODUCTION

In industrial facilities, electrical systems are the foundation of daily operations, powering essential equipment such as production machinery, lighting, mechanical systems, and control systems (Roche, 2024). These systems are critical for ensuring continuous productivity, maintaining workplace safety, and sustaining operational efficiency. However, due to their complexity and constant use, they are vulnerable to deterioration, equipment malfunction, and catastrophic failure. Poor or ineffective equipment maintenance has been identified as a major electrical safety concern in manufacturing facilities, often resulting in production downtime, costly repairs, and serious safety hazards (Wilk, 2025).

To mitigate these risks, Electrical Preventive Maintenance (EPM) has emerged as a proactive approach to inspecting, testing, and maintaining electrical systems to prevent failures, enhance efficiency, and ensure safety (Stamford Electrical, 2025). Routine preventive maintenance improves system reliability, extends equipment lifespan, and enhances operational performance (Ronika, 2024). Despite these advantages, many industrial facilities still underutilize EPM due to budget limitations, outdated planning methods, and insufficient resources.

The consequences of inadequate electrical maintenance have been widely documented. Electrical distribution equipment remains a leading ignition source of industrial fires, resulting in significant losses and operational disruptions (McGree, 2023). In the Philippines, the Bureau of Fire Protection similarly reports many fire incidents caused by electrical problems, highlighting the importance of systematic preventive maintenance. While international standards such as the IEEE Recommended Practice for Electrical Equipment Maintenance and NFPA 70B provide comprehensive procedures for preventive maintenance, there is no equally established and detailed local standard in the Philippine context.

The Philippine Electrical Code primarily focuses on safety requirements for electrical installation rather than ongoing preventive maintenance practices. In many industrial zones, compliance is monitored through the Certificate of Electrical Inspection (CEI) process, which verifies conformity with safety codes but provides limited guidance for structured preventive maintenance programs. Existing literature confirms that EPM contributes to safety, energy efficiency, and equipment reliability; however, limited studies have examined EPM implementation from an integrated engineering management perspective, particularly in industrial facilities in the Philippine context.

To address this gap, this study evaluated EPM using the 5Ms of Management Framework: Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money in selected industrial facilities in Carmelray Industrial Park 1 in Canlubang, Calamba, Laguna. Specifically, the study

aimed to determine the level of implementation of EPM across the five dimensions of management, identify the challenges affecting its effective implementation, examine how these challenges influence electrical system reliability and sustainability, and propose strategies to strengthen EPM implementation in industrial facilities.

This study is limited to examining preventive maintenance strategies applied specifically to electrical systems in selected industrial facilities. The findings are based on survey responses from facility managers and maintenance engineers and do not include detailed technical testing or predictive maintenance analysis.

Research Framework

This study utilized a theoretical framework to establish the connection between engineering management principles and the effectiveness of EPM in industrial operations. Specifically, the study adopted the 5Ms of Management (Oni, 2024) — Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money, as a lens to examine how workforce competence, equipment condition, procedural adherence, material availability, and financial allocation influence maintenance outcomes and system reliability in industrial facilities.

Rooted in the Ishikawa cause-and-effect model in quality management, the 5Ms provide a structured approach for evaluating preventive maintenance implementation and balancing essential maintenance resources (Hupjé, 2024). Previous studies also confirm that the effectiveness of preventive maintenance is strongly influenced by workforce capability, processes, materials, and financial resources, which align with the 5Ms of Management (de Campos and Simon, 2019; Malhotra et al., 2021; Alzeraif and Cheaitou, 2024; Zhao et al., 2022).

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design to assess the implementation and effectiveness of EPM practices in selected industrial facilities. The design enabled the systematic collection and analysis of quantifiable data to describe the current level of EPM implementation, identify prevailing challenges, and evaluate their influence on system reliability and sustainability. A structured survey questionnaire served as the primary research instrument using a 4-point Likert scale to quantify responses across the 5Ms of Management: Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Questions

This research aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Electrical Preventive Maintenance (EPM) in achieving sustainable system reliability within industrial facilities. To accomplish this, the following research questions were raised:

1. What is the level of implementation of EPM on system reliability and sustainability in industrial facilities, considering the dimensions of Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money
2. How do challenges related to each of the 5Ms of Management hinder the effective implementation of EPM?
3. In what ways do these challenges influence electrical system reliability and sustainability?
4. What strategies can be employed to address these challenges and enhance EPM effectiveness?

METHODOLOGY

Sampling Method

The study was conducted among PEZA-registered industrial firms located in Carmelray Industrial Park 1 in Canlubang, Calamba, Laguna. Out of the 61 industrial locators, 26 PEZA-registered firms were included in the study due to their regulatory requirement to secure a Certificate of Electrical Inspection (CEI), which involves routine electrical testing and inspection related to preventive maintenance. The respondents consisted of facility managers, maintenance engineers, or technicians directly involved in EPM activities. A total enumeration sampling method was used, inviting one qualified respondent from each firm to participate in the survey.

Data Collection Instruments

A structured survey questionnaire was used as the primary research instrument to evaluate the implementation of EPM practices. The instrument was developed based on the 5Ms of Management framework, with 25 closed-ended items, consisting of five indicators for each dimension. The Man component assessed personnel competency and training; Machine evaluated equipment condition and reliability; Method examined documented procedures and compliance; Material measured the availability of tools, spare parts, and testing equipment; and Money assessed financial allocation and investment in EPM resources. Responses were measured using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 4 – Fully Implemented, 3 – Partially Implemented, 2 – Rarely Implemented, and 1 – Not Implemented at All.

The questionnaire was validated by an electrical engineering expert and pilot-tested with four engineers from non-respondent facilities. The reliability test yielded a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, indicating high internal consistency.

Data Analysis

Data collected from the survey were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods, including percentages and median values, to determine the level of EPM implementation across the five dimensions of the 5Ms of Management. Median scores were used to identify the lowest-rated indicators representing key challenges affecting EPM practices. The qualitative responses from open-ended items were also reviewed to provide additional context for the quantitative findings. The results were synthesized to determine how challenges across the 5Ms influence system reliability and sustainability and to develop strategies for improving EPM implementation.

Table 1. Data Analysis Matrix

Research Question	Type of Data	Research Instrument	Data Analysis
1. What is the level of implementation of Electrical Preventive Maintenance (EPM) on system reliability and sustainability in industrial facilities, considering the dimensions of: Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money	Ordinal (Likert-scale responses)	Primary Data: Online Survey Questionnaire via Google Forms	Descriptive Statistical Analysis: Percentages and Median values per 5M to determine the level of implementation.
2. How do challenges related to each of the 5Ms of Management hinder the effective implementation of EPM?	Ordinal (Likert-scale responses)	Primary Data: Online Survey Questionnaire via Google Forms	Descriptive Statistical Analysis: Median values per 5M to identify the lowest-rated performing item representing key implementation challenges.
3. In what ways do these challenges influence electrical system reliability and sustainability?	Mixed (Quantitative & Qualitative)	Primary Data: Online Survey Questionnaire Open and Closed-ended Questions	Descriptive Statistical Analysis: Percentage Open and Closed-ended Responses
4. What strategies can be employed to address these challenges and enhance EPM effectiveness?	Integrated (Based on RQ1–RQ3 results)	Derived from the synthesis of survey results	Analysis of results from RQ1–RQ3 to propose evidence-based strategies for improving EPM effectiveness across the 5Ms.

Table 2. Interpretation of the 4-Point Scale for the Level of Implementation of EPM

Median Range	Interpretation	Description
3.50 – 4.00	Fully Implemented	The findings indicated that respondents strongly agreed that Electrical Preventive Maintenance (EPM) practices are consistently and effectively implemented in the organization. Implementation was systematic, monitored, and sustained.
2.50 – 3.49	Partially Implemented	The findings indicated that respondents perceived EPM practices as being implemented in the organization, but with inconsistencies, revealing areas that required improvement. Some aspects were implemented effectively while others required improvement or closer monitoring.
1.50 – 2.49	Rarely Implemented	The findings revealed that respondents perceived EPM practices as occasionally implemented, with insufficient monitoring and consistent execution across facilities. Implementation occurred only when issues arose.
1.00 – 1.49	Not Implemented at All	The findings revealed that respondents perceived that EPM practices were generally not implemented in their organization. Maintenance activities were mostly reactive rather than preventive.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the effectiveness of EPM in achieving sustainable system reliability in industrial facilities. This chapter presents and discusses the results derived from the survey, supported by qualitative responses from the participants. The integration of both quantitative and qualitative data provides a more comprehensive analysis of EPM implementation and the challenges affecting its effectiveness. The findings are presented according to the study objectives, including the level of EPM implementation, the challenges across the 5Ms of Management, their influence on system reliability and sustainability, and the strategies to strengthen EPM implementation.

Level of Implementation of EPM on System Reliability and Sustainability

Table 3 summarizes the level of EPM implementation across the five management dimensions based on the responses of 26 participants.

Table 3. Level of Implementation of EPM per 5Ms on System Reliability and Sustainability

DIMENSION	MEDIAN	INTERPRETATION
MAN	3.00	Partially Implemented
MACHINE	4.00	Fully Implemented
METHOD	4.00	Fully Implemented
MATERIAL	3.00	Partially Implemented
MONEY	3.00	Partially Implemented
Overall Median	3.00	Partially Implemented

The results indicate that EPM is generally partially implemented among the surveyed industrial facilities. The Machine and Method dimensions were rated fully implemented, reflecting strong emphasis on equipment servicing, maintenance planning, documentation, and compliance-driven procedures. In contrast, the Man, Material, and Money dimensions were rated partially implemented, suggesting limitations in workforce development, resource readiness, and financial support. This pattern indicates that EPM implementation remains more technically focused than management-driven, which may limit its long-term sustainability and effectiveness. Table 4 presents the percentage distribution of responses across the four levels of implementation.

Table 4. Percentage of Level of Implementation per 5Ms

DIMENSION	LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION			
	FULLY	PARTIALLY	RARELY	NOT AT ALL
MAN	44.62 %	54.62%	0.77%	0.00%
MACHINE	60.77 %	36.15%	3.07%	0.00%
METHOD	68.46 %	30.77%	0.77%	0.00%
MATERIAL	36.92%	56.92%	6.15%	0.00%
MONEY	48.46 %	50.00%	1.54%	0.00%

The results show that most responses fall under fully implemented and partially implemented categories, particularly for the Machine and Method dimensions. Meanwhile, the Man, Material, and Money dimensions show higher percentages under partially implemented, indicating areas where improvements in personnel training, resource availability, and financial allocation may be required. Similar findings were reported by Malhotra et al. (2021) and Alzeraif and Cheaitou (2024), who emphasized that workforce capability, resource availability, and financial investment significantly influence the effectiveness of preventive maintenance and long-term system reliability. These results suggest that while industrial facilities generally maintain adequate technical maintenance procedures, the sustainability of EPM programs may be constrained by

managerial factors such as workforce development, resource readiness, and long-term financial planning.

Challenges Related to Each of the 5Ms that Hinder the Effective Implementation of EPM

The challenges affecting EPM implementation were identified based on the lowest median indicators in each of the five management dimensions, supported by qualitative responses from the participants.

For the Man dimension, gaps were observed in training participation, professional certification, and the application of EPM standards. Although maintenance personnel are generally capable of performing routine tasks, limited professional development and certification opportunities may reduce maintenance quality and consistency.

In the Machine dimension, the primary challenge was the limited availability of spare electrical equipment or backup units, which may prolong downtime during equipment failure. While regular inspection and testing practices are generally implemented, insufficient equipment redundancy increases operational risk and limits the facility's ability to maintain operational continuity.

For the Method dimension, weaknesses were observed in inventory management and maintenance documentation systems. Incomplete records and inconsistent tracking reduce the organization's ability to analyze maintenance trends, monitor equipment condition, and implement proactive improvements in preventive maintenance practices.

In the Material dimension, challenges were associated with the availability of spare parts, calibrated testing instruments, and proper storage of maintenance tools and equipment. Limited access to diagnostic equipment may delay preventive maintenance activities and reduce the accuracy of equipment inspection and testing.

Finally, the Money dimension revealed limitations in budget allocation for training, equipment modernization, and replacement of aging electrical assets. Preventive maintenance was often treated as an operational expense rather than a long-term investment, which may constrain the sustainability and effectiveness of EPM programs.

These findings indicate that the challenges affecting EPM implementation are not limited to technical maintenance activities but extend to broader managerial and organizational factors. Limitations in workforce capability, equipment redundancy, maintenance procedures, resource availability, and financial allocation collectively influence the consistency and effectiveness of preventive maintenance practices in industrial facilities. In the Philippine context, preventive maintenance in some facilities is often conducted only when operational issues arise or when regulatory documentation is required for the issuance of safety certifications, rather than as a continuously implemented preventive program. This practice may result in maintenance activities becoming reactive rather than proactive.

This observation is consistent with common maintenance practices in many industrial facilities, where preventive maintenance programs are often implemented primarily to satisfy regulatory inspection and documentation requirements rather than as fully integrated reliability management strategies. This finding also aligns with studies emphasizing that effective maintenance programs require the integration of organizational strategy, workforce capability, and resource planning to support sustainable industrial operations (de Campos & Simon, 2019).

Influence of Challenges on System Reliability and Sustainability

The results indicate that challenges across the 5Ms collectively influence electrical system reliability and sustainability. Maintenance effectiveness depends not only on technical procedures but also on workforce competence, resource availability, and financial support.

Personnel capability and competency directly affect the consistency of maintenance activities. The findings indicated that 85% of the surveyed facilities relied on in-house maintenance personnel to conduct daily or routine EPM activities, while 15% reported a combination of in-house personnel and external contractors. While reliance on internal personnel provides operational familiarity and faster response to maintenance needs, limitations in training, certification, and access to specialized diagnostic tools may affect the consistency and quality of maintenance implementation. For more complex annual or major EPM activities, several facilities relied on external contractors, primarily due to the limited availability of calibrated testing instruments and specialized diagnostic equipment. The responses also indicated that EPM was primarily conducted to ensure system reliability, prevent equipment failure, and maintain operational continuity, with regulatory compliance serving as a supporting factor. These motivations show that preventive maintenance is viewed not only as a compliance requirement but also as an operational necessity for sustaining reliable electrical system performance.

Open-ended responses further revealed how challenges across the 5Ms influence system reliability and sustainability. In the Man dimension, limitations in training and certification may reduce maintenance quality. In the Machine dimension, limited spare equipment or backup units may extend downtime during failures. In the Method dimension, incomplete documentation and inconsistent scheduling reduce preventive maintenance effectiveness. In the Material dimension, limited spare parts and diagnostic tools may delay inspections and increase the risk of undetected deterioration. In the Money dimension, financial constraints limit investments in training, equipment modernization, and preventive maintenance programs.

These findings indicate that preventive maintenance effectiveness depends on the integrated management of manpower, procedures, materials, equipment resources, and financial support. When these elements are not managed in a coordinated manner, preventive maintenance may become reactive rather than proactive. This observation is consistent with NFPA 70B (2023) and Kumar et al. (2020), which emphasize that

workforce competency, resource allocation, and financial investment are essential for maintaining reliable electrical system performance.

Therefore, achieving sustainable electrical system reliability requires not only the implementation of preventive maintenance procedures but also the coordinated management of organizational resources across the five dimensions of management.

Recommended Strategies for Strengthening EPM Implementation

Based on the results of the study, particularly the challenges identified across the five dimensions of management, several strategies are recommended to strengthen the implementation of EPM in industrial facilities.

In this study, strategic actions refer to long-term management directions that establish priorities, policies, and resource commitments necessary to sustain effective EPM. These include strengthening workforce capability, improving equipment reliability, institutionalizing standardized maintenance procedures, ensuring resource readiness, and allocating sustainable financial support.

Tactical or operational actions translate these strategic priorities into day-to-day maintenance practices such as scheduled inspections, calibration of diagnostic instruments, management of spare parts and maintenance tools, documentation of maintenance activities, and implementation of approved maintenance budgets.

The integration of strategic and operational actions across the 5Ms of Management provides a structured approach to strengthening EPM implementation and sustaining reliable electrical system performance.

Table 5. Strategic and Tactical Recommendations for Strengthening EPM Implementation in Industrial Facilities

Dimension	Strategic Focus	Tactical / Operational Actions	Responsible Unit	Success Indicator
Man	Develop and enhance a competent and safety-oriented maintenance workforce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a maintenance competency framework and maintain training and qualification records - Conduct regular training, seminars, and refresher courses related to EPM, code compliance, energy efficiency, and 	Top Management, Human Resource, and Maintenance Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Percentage of trained personnel. -Reduced reliance on external contractors. -Reduction in maintenance-related incidents.

		sustainable electrical system operation.		
Machine	Improve equipment reliability and minimize downtime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop an equipment criticality list and maintain an inventory of critical spare parts. - Establish supplier contract agreements for critical spare parts and maintenance services. 	Maintenance Department and Procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reduced equipment downtime. -Faster repair turnaround time and availability rate of equipment critical spares.
Method	Institutionalize standardized and compliant EPM procedure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardize and digitize EPM procedures; implement EPM scheduling and documentation systems aligned with PEZA, DOLE, PEC, and NFPA 70B. 	Maintenance Department and Compliance Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Completion rate of scheduled PM activities, audit compliance results. -Accuracy and completeness of maintenance records.
Material	Ensure the availability and readiness of maintenance resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish minimum stock levels of tools and spare parts. - Provide calibrated tools, test instruments, and adequate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). - Implement regular calibration schedule for testing instruments and inspection schedules for PPE. 	Maintenance Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Availability rate of tools and spare parts, calibration compliance rate, and reduced maintenance delays
Money	Sustain EPM through long-term financial planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allocate a dedicated budget for EPM activities. - Identify maintenance activities under Operational Expenses (OPEX) and Capital 	Top Management, Maintenance, and Finance Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stability of EPM budget, reduction in corrective maintenance costs, improved maintenance cost predictability.

		<p>Expenditures (CAPEX).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement lifecycle costing and cost-benefit analysis for maintenance planning and equipment replacement. - Establish an emergency maintenance fund for unexpected equipment failures. - Allocate financial resources for personnel training and professional development related to EPM. 		
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Effective EPM implementation requires strategic-tactical alignment across the five management dimensions. Strategic priorities focus on workforce capability, equipment reliability, standardized procedures, resource readiness, and sustainable financial investment, ensuring that preventive maintenance is treated as a long-term management function.

Strong top management support remains essential because leadership commitment influences policy enforcement, resource allocation, and organizational maintenance culture. Consistent with NFPA 70B (2023), sustained management involvement supports reliable electrical system performance. Previous studies also show that structured maintenance strategies improve operational efficiency and equipment life (Rahman et al., 2025; Sanusi, 2019).

Overall, preventive maintenance should be viewed as a strategic investment that reduces operational risk and supports sustainable industrial performance. This study demonstrates that sustainable electrical system reliability in industrial facilities requires the integration of engineering management principles within EPM programs, emphasizing the coordinated management of manpower, equipment, procedures, resources, and financial support.

These recommendations highlight that effective preventive maintenance requires not only technical maintenance activities but also strategic organizational support to ensure long-term system reliability, operational continuity, safety compliance, and the sustainable management of electrical assets in industrial facilities.

Research Implication

The findings of this study contribute to the field of engineering management by demonstrating that the effectiveness of EPM extends beyond technical maintenance practices and depends significantly on the integrated management of manpower, resources, procedures, equipment, and financial support. By applying the 5Ms of Management as an analytical framework, this study provides a structured approach for evaluating preventive maintenance implementation in industrial facilities. The results highlight that sustainable electrical system reliability requires balanced investment not only in technical maintenance activities but also in workforce capability, resource readiness, and organizational support. This integrated perspective may serve as a practical reference for industrial managers, maintenance engineers, and regulatory bodies in strengthening preventive maintenance strategies in developing industrial contexts.

Conclusions

This study evaluated the implementation, challenges, and impact of EPM in industrial facilities using the 5Ms of Management framework: Man, Machine, Method, Material, and Money. The findings indicated that preventive maintenance practices were generally recognized and implemented; however, their effectiveness varied across management dimensions. Technical aspects such as equipment servicing and maintenance procedures were more consistently implemented, while managerial dimensions related to workforce capability, resource readiness, and financial allocation were only partially implemented. These results demonstrate that the effectiveness of EPM depends not only on technical maintenance practices but also on coordinated management support, resource planning, and workforce capability.

The study also revealed that most facilities relied on in-house personnel for daily or routine EPM activities, while major or annual EPM was frequently outsourced to external contractors due to limited internal diagnostic equipment and specialized expertise. While outsourcing helps ensure technical accuracy and regulatory compliance, strengthening internal maintenance capability remains important for sustaining long-term electrical system reliability. Overall, the findings confirm that preventive maintenance should be viewed not only as a compliance requirement but also as a strategic engineering management function that supports reliable and sustainable industrial operations. This study highlights that strengthening preventive maintenance implementation through integrated management of manpower, equipment, procedures, resources, and financial support can significantly improve electrical system reliability and support the long-term sustainability of industrial operations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to strengthen the effective implementation of EPM in industrial facilities.

1. Enhance workforce capability by implementing structured training, certification, and refresher programs aligned with NFPA 70B and the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC) to improve maintenance competence and reduce dependence on external contractors.
2. Institutionalize standardized maintenance procedures by implementing digital documentation systems, regular inspection schedules, and calibration of testing instruments to ensure accountability, traceability, and regulatory compliance.
3. Improve resource planning and asset management by maintaining adequate spare parts inventory, diagnostic tools, and maintenance equipment to support timely and effective preventive maintenance activities.
4. Strengthen financial and organizational support by allocating sustainable budgets for preventive maintenance, workforce development, and equipment modernization, recognizing EPM as a long-term investment in system reliability.
5. Encourage future research and industry collaboration to further examine preventive maintenance practices across broader industrial sectors and integrate data-driven maintenance indicators, predictive monitoring technologies, and sustainability metrics.
6. Strengthen institutional and regulatory support for EPM implementation. Regulatory and professional bodies such as PEZA, DOLE, and the Institute of Integrated Electrical Engineers of the Philippines (IIEE) may consider developing localized EPM guidelines, training accreditation systems, and standardized maintenance reporting frameworks aligned with existing standards such as NFPA 70B and the Philippine Electrical Code. Establishing national or industry-based EPM guidelines may promote consistent maintenance practices, strengthen regulatory compliance, and support long-term electrical system reliability and sustainability in industrial operations.

Overall, integrating EPM within the five dimensions of management promotes coordinated management of workforce capability, procedures, resources, and financial support, thereby strengthening electrical system reliability and supporting sustainable industrial operations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that informed consent was secured from all participants and that all collected data were treated with anonymity. The study complied with plagiarism standards, ensuring objective analysis and the use of findings strictly for research purposes.

Furthermore, this study observed strict ethical standards to protect the rights and privacy of respondents. Respondents were informed about the purpose and procedures of the research and provided informed consent prior to participation. Participation was voluntary, and respondents could withdraw at any time without consequence. All responses were treated with strict confidentiality and anonymity, and the collected data were used solely

for academic purposes. Data handling complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring secure storage and restricted access to research data.

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